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“CHALLENGES AND OPPORTUNITIES OF RURAL FARM SCHOOLS”

Rural farm schools also known as Family Farm Schools were introduced to our country almost forty years ago. These schools are described as unique but holistic and offer practical training in agriculture and fishery education. The concept of these schools is patterned after a European model on integral formation to prepare young people for farm entrepreneurship and eventually as agents of rural development.

In the Philippines, R.A. 10618 or the Rural Farm School Act of 2013 was enacted. The Department of Education is considered as the primary implementing government agency of this law. Rural public farm schools were then established in most provinces all over the Philippines. Since 2015, its curriculum offers alternative delivery mode which is flexible, non-traditional and combines various formats that suit the needs and interests of secondary school students.

With the implementation of these rural farm schools, several challenges were encountered like limited land and water resources and access to information and communication technologies, lack of farming and fishery facilities, scarcity of professional teachers specializing in agriculture and fishery arts. Socio-economic factors such as high incidence of poverty and malnutrition in rural areas which affect learning as well as school's accessibility and distance.

Along with the challenges stated, opportunities are also observed. These doors of opportunities offer rural farm schools an edge. These farm schools enhance the agri-preneurial skills among students who are sons and daughters of farmers and fisherfolks. By increased productivity and profitability, local economy will improve as well as environmental sustainability is achieved. With the approval of Farm Tourism Development Act, farm schools may now have access to funding and resources.

The failure or success of these rural farm schools is not the sole responsibility of the government. It is through the concerted efforts of the stakeholders and relevant interested parties. Everyone has its role to play in making agriculture vibrant and relevant. Farming for the future depends on the youth of today. Food security today is not a guaranty of food security for tomorrow. To end, rural farm schools are guided by the principles of Learning by doing, Doing to farm, Farming to live, Living to serve”.

